

How Teachers' perceptions shape the provision of support to Learners with Mild Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder in Inclusive Primary Schools of Lusaka

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ABSTRACT

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Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by inattention, hyperactivity and impulsivity, which causes functional impairment. The study unveiled a conceptual framework for supporting teachers teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools of Lusaka- Zambia, arising from their own perceptions of the learners with ADHD they teach. A descriptive design was used. The sample size involved 25 participants, which included 18 Class Teachers, 3 School Administrators and 4 MoE Officials. Homogeneous purposive sampling techniques was used to select class teachers and school administrators and expert purposive sampling techniques to select all MoE officials responsible for special education in the district. Data were collected using in-depth interviews guides, Focus Group Discussion guides and observation checklist. Analysis was thematic. Mixed perceptions were recorded from participants showing that few teachers had adequate understanding and most of the teachers had limited understanding due to inadequate preparation in Special education. Inadequate understanding of the condition largely influenced how they perceived learners with ADHD and how much support they provided to them. To address the negative perceptions on teaching of learners with ADHD in inclusive primary schools, Kabwe's Framework (KF) of supporting teachers and learners with mild ADHD in inclusive schools was designed in order to promote inclusive education. The design recommends the participation and collaboration of various stakeholders as well as improved school environment that accommodates learners with ADHD.

KEYWORDS:

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, Inclusive education, Teacher understanding.

INTRODUCTION

Hyperactivity refers to behavior such as fidgeting with hands or feet, difficulty in sitting still for extended periods of time and talking excessively. Impulsivity includes behavior such as blurting out answers before questions have been completed. The purpose of this study was to explore the teachers' understanding of teaching learners with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) in Zambian Primary Inclusive Schools so that interventions are put in place to address the situation that may arise from possible negative experiences. Learners with ADHD are among the least unidentified group of learners in Zambian schools. Konstantin et al. (2021) states that ADHD is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by inattention, hyperactivity and impulsivity causing functional impairment.

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Hamilton et al. (2016) adds that ADHD is a disorder characterized by inattentiveness, hyperactivity and impulsivity. Inattention entails executive deficits that involve off – task behaviors and poor organization, whereas hyperactivity is demonstrated by fidgeting, excessive talking and inability to regulate stimuli. Children and adolescents with ADHD frequently have co-morbid psychiatric disorders, which include oppositional defiant disorders, conduct disorders, depression, anxiety disorder and developmental disorders, speech and language delay and learning disabilities (Kleynhans, 2005). From these characteristics of ADHD, managing a classroom with both children with ADHD and children without ADHD maybe very involving for the class teacher (Kabwe, Muzata and Simalalo, 2024).

It is estimated that there is at least one learner with mild ADHD in every regular education classroom (Barkley, 2005). Globally, the prevalence of ADHD worldwide was 7.2% of both children and adults who received diagnosis of ADHD. It accounted for about 5% in children of school going age worldwide (APA, 2013). Approximately, about 11% of the children between the ages 4 to 7 are diagnosed with ADHD.

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According to Joshi and Angolkar (2018), mild ADHD is more common in boys than in girls and affects 5-11% of students in the United States (APA, 2013).

In Zambia, Tembo (2014) recorded the prevalence of 9.1 of children with symptoms of ADHD. Further, Sikabule (2019) found that there was an increase of 14% of the total population of the learners with the symptoms of ADHD in selected primary schools of Pemba District in Southern province.

Available literature shows a combination of perceptions towards learners with ADHD. Globally, Shroff *et al.* (2017) conducted a study on misunderstanding about ADHD in India. The study found that teachers assumed that ADHD could be cured with dietary management. The teachers' feedback also revealed an inadequate understanding of knowledge concerning stimulating medication for learners with ADHD. Further, a study by Dwarika *et al.* (2021) provided a description of teachers' understanding of ADHD and their experiences of supporting learners with ADHD. The findings revealed that teachers' understanding of ADHD appeared limited. The stigma of ADHD created a reluctance from care givers toward pharmacological treatment.

Another study by Guerra *et al.* (2017) on examining teachers' knowledge, misconceptions, and concerns about learners with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) in United Kingdom found that the majority of teachers did not have coursework related to learners with ADHD in their preparation programme due to limited understanding of such learners in their classrooms. Teachers indicated inadequate administrative support and access to professional development regarding learners with ADHD.

Jaye *et al.* (2020) conducted a study on understanding and perceptions of ADHD amongst Foundation Phase teachers at an independent school in Johannesburg, South Africa. The study revealed that teachers had limited knowledge with regard to the symptoms of ADHD, they had a fair understanding about the treatment about ADHD and their knowledge about the associated features of ADHD was limited. Many misconceptions exist about the disorder, mainly those surrounding the causes and treatment available (Akahtani, 2013). The different types of ADHD were poorly understood (Kos, 2009). Furthermore, it was reported that exposure to children with ADHD and higher number of ADHD workshops attended and ADHD articles reads were beneficial to the teachers' overall knowledge about ADHD. Years of experiences and the age of the teacher were not associated with a greater knowledge about ADHD. These findings agree with a study by Ntuli (2014) on the understanding of ADHD in Ekurhuleni district in Johannesburg that revealed that both mainstream and remedial schools' negative attitudes about ADHD affected these learners and educators' knowledge was limited. This situation may be similar to teachers' understanding of

ADHD in a classroom in Zambia, hence the need for the study.

The study by Ewe (2019) indicated that teachers felt less able to build emotional bonds and cooperation with learners with mild ADHD compared to learners with no mild ADHD. Mainly the teachers' limited understanding of these learners influenced this. Further, Ewe (2019) revealed that teachers with limited understanding of learners with mild ADHD failed to control the behavior and stage reactions of these learners in the classroom. Neil (2014) revealed that teachers often held negative beliefs regarding behavior problems exhibited by learners with mild ADHD. In addition, some teachers tended to be pessimistic about teaching these learners, and felt that they required extra time and effort to teach them. Teachers were therefore, responsible for creating an environment to academic, social and emotional success for learners with mild ADHD in inclusive schools. Spasovski (2010) revealed that practicing inclusive education is strongly determined by the teacher's perceptions on learners with special needs and perception of their capability and limitation. Nevertheless, it is not known if the situation was the same in Lusaka where this study was conducted.

Moore, Russel and Arnell (2017) conducted a study on educators' experiences of managing students with mild ADHD in United Kingdom. The study revealed that some factors such as stigmatization hindered the learners' ability to learn and affected them in the classroom. This was in line with Richard (2001) who indicated that negative stigma attached to any diagnosed disorder remains a reality, regardless of etiology or severity. Thus, there was need to remove these negative stigmas if learners with mild ADHD were to learn effectively.

Lawrence *et al.* (2017) conducted a study on Teachers' Experiences and Perceptions of students with ADHD in Columbia, United States. The findings revealed that culture and gender influenced teacher perceptions, and mild ADHD classroom strategies were based on anecdotal experience. Teachers experienced guilty and worry while negotiating the learners' needs, school system constraints and family issues. However, the study focused on both teachers' experiences and perceptions of learners with mild ADHD Disorder, while the current study only focused on the implication on teachers 'negative perceptions of the teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools in Zambia.

Naidoo (2019) noted that teachers had different perceptions when teaching learners with mild ADHD, which often stemmed from lack of knowledge or understanding of mild ADHD in schools. However, Lawrence *et al.* (2017) on Teachers' experiences and perceptions of students with ADHD, revealed that culture and gender influenced teacher perceptions of learners with ADHD in classroom strategies were based on anecdotal experience. Teachers experienced guilty and worry while negotiating the learner's needs, school

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system constraints and family issues. Teachers' attitude towards learners with mild ADHD is overwhelmingly negative, and they seem to lack a deeper understanding of mild ADHD and this affect their teaching (Mthethwa, 2016). Similarly, the study by Mueller *et.al.* (2012) indicated that the negative perceptions on learners with mild ADHD had a significant impact on the wellbeing and self-stigmatization of these learners.

In Kenya, Omunda (2021) conducted a qualitative transcendental phenomenological study to obtain a comprehensive understanding of special education teachers' beliefs and daily experiences working with learners with mild ADHD in inclusive classrooms. The study revealed that special education teachers described their collaborations with the general education teachers as part of the positive experiences when working with learners with mild ADHD, but they also noted that this collaboration possess some challenges. Both special education teachers and general teachers teaching learners with mild ADHD were not adequately trained to deal with challenges presented by students with mild ADHD. Further participants believed that learners with mild ADHD could be successful in the academic environment if given the necessary support. Most of the participants expressed their beliefs in medication for students with mild ADHD. They indicated that consistent medication for learners with mild ADHD contributes to their success in the academic environment. They described participants who took medication as under control, while those who were inconsistent in medication use often remained behind academically.

In Zambia, Sikabule (2019) revealed that teachers experienced many challenges when teaching pupils with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools. The study found that teachers experienced challenges such as learners always run up and down disturbing other learners, lacked of concentration that caused poor performance and slow grasping of concepts due to inadequate concentration. Other challenges experienced included learners with mild ADHD over reacting in certain situations, which disturbed the flow of lessons. Further, learners exhibited interruption and restless behavior thereby making teaching and learning a challenge and did not take learning seriously hence difficult to manage the class. Additionally, learners with mild ADHD were always trouble makers, noisemakers, slow in completing tasks, lacked specialized teaching materials and were stigmatized, and this made them not to like school. It therefore calls for teachers' understanding of the challenges so that they could provide the right support to the learners.

Cho and Blair (2017) conducted a study and evaluated that there was a multicomponent function-based intervention for learners identified with mild ADHD in a private special education school. The focus of this intervention involved modifying classroom activities to decrease learners' disruptive behaviors and increase their academic

engagement. Teacher participants took part in a two-hour training session that focused on functional behavior assessments, implementing interventions with fidelity, and monitoring the students' behavior and academic progress. The intervention strategies were evidence-based, aligned with the learner motivation and context where the behavior occurred, and were implemented with fidelity. Cho and Blair (2017) found a decrease in target problem behaviors and increased academic engagement across academic subjects. While this strategy was effective, it was not known if it could work in Zambian primary inclusive schools where the current study was conducted.

According to Murphy (2015), learners with mild ADHD can be productive in general education classrooms if teachers recognized and employed efficient teaching and behavioral management approaches. Nonetheless, general education classroom teachers from many parts of the world voiced various concerns about teaching learners with mild ADHD, citing issues such as inadequate training and lack of administrative support (Guerra et al., 2017). Teachers played an ongoing and pivotal role in learner's lives in the area of recognizing features (Layton et al, 2018) communicating with specialists and managing the learners' behavior in a classroom environment. As such, it was vital that teachers have an in-depth understanding of mild ADHD.

Dwarika and Braud (2020) points out that teachers were supposed to show love and support to learners with mild ADHD in inclusive schools by knowing their learners, listen to them, encourage them, helping them when they needed them most, being there for them, give them space when they needed it, connect with them, appreciate them and show that they cared for them. Further, Tembo (2014) unveiled that the amount of education and training the teacher had about mild ADHD, affected their willingness to seek and apply strategies and techniques. Similarly, Dwarika and Braude (2020) indicated that Professional Development strategies were deemed useful in supporting learners with mild ADHD if they were relevant and appropriated within the systemic context of their classrooms.

Another study by Makunga (2023) revealed that most of the teachers with appropriate training in catch-up strategies had a general understanding of remedial teaching. Furthermore, most of the teachers and learners emphasized that remedial lessons were intellectually enriching experiences to them. Additionally, Braude and Dwarika (2020) revealed that some of the strategies used by teachers when teaching learners with disabilities involved giving the learners extra time to complete work or seating them alone or limiting distractions for them. Similarly, the study by Mavuso (2014) reported that South African teachers used extra lessons, extra work, differentiating of teaching styles and peer support as strategies in mainstream schools. Reiber and McLaughlin (2004) found that learners were paired with tutors who

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provided guidance and immediate feedback, which led to increase on-task behavior, decrease in fidgeting and increased academic performance on tests among the learners. Wender (2000) indicated that most learners with mild ADHD showed certain forms of emotional problems, such as mood swings and cycles, which made their behavior unpredictable. Hence, teachers of these learners were supposed to display good relationship towards them and be patient while teaching them. Ravi (2016) mentioned that in order to foster personal-social competences, teachers needed to develop an understanding of their learners and ensure that all learners were treated fairly, valued and are exposed to a wider of personal and social learning experiences.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Research studies conducted globally and Zambia show that learners with mild ADHD exhibit poor educational outcomes, distracting behaviors, and deficits in interpersonal skills that affect their academic performance than those without disabilities in the general education classrooms (Rogers et al., 2015; Ntengwe, 2018 and Sikabule, 2019). However, these studies do not explore, for example, the teachers' understanding of teaching learners with mild ADHD and how such understanding influence their perceptions and support for learners with ADHD in inclusive primary schools. Further, there is still a knowledge gap regarding the nature of support teachers provide to learners with mild ADHD in Zambian primary schools. The existence of this knowledge gap motivated the present study.

Research Questions:

This study endeavored to answer two key questions as follows:

1. How do teachers' understanding of ADHD influence the way they teach learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools in Lusaka District?
2. What conceptual framework would be appropriate to support teachers and learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools in Lusaka district?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Self - efficacy theory by Bandura (1997), guided this study. Self- efficacy involves the way an individual perceives their ability to have control over their environment and their ability to carry out effort to manage and deal with environmental circumstances. High self-efficacy lead to an individual to believe in their ability to gain control over their environment and in return produce change, while low sense of self-efficacy results in an individual avoiding their ability to produce a change or persevere through the change which they may experience. In the context of the study, the teachers' understanding influences the perception of teachers towards learners with mild ADHD. In turn, teachers' perception influences the nature of support strategies provided to

learners with mild ADHD. Minimum support is based on the already built perception. Thus, the teachers' perceptions of learners with ADHD may influence the way they exert control over the classroom environment specifically over the learners and in turn, their self-efficacy may influence how they interact with learners who experience mild ADHD issues in schools (Bandura, 1997).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Kivunja & Kuyuini (2017) whose study employed the qualitative interpretivism research states that a research paradigm represents the researcher's worldview, perspectives, or thinking about the issue under research. It represents the researcher's abstract beliefs and principles that shape his or her understanding of the world. In other words, a research paradigm is the researcher's lens that enables them to view the world (Adu and Okeke, 2022). An interpretivism research paradigm was used because of its descriptive in nature, focusing on the collection of in-depth data, non-use of numbers and ability to ease the interpretation of data collected from the study sites or field. Subjective meaning of the research was developed through interaction with participants in the field they live and work in order to understand the reality of the phenomenon. This study employed a descriptive research design using a qualitative approach. This design was used based on the rationale that the data collected contained information about people's views, attitudes, and opinions on teachers' understanding of teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools. This approach recognizes the importance of the subjective human creation of meaning but does not reject outright some ideas of objectivity (Mtonga, Serenje, & Chipindi, 2020).

The target population comprised teachers who teach learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools, school administrators and MoE officials responsible for special education. The researcher's choice of this population was based on the belief that it could provide the necessary data needed for the study. The participants were believed to have sufficient experiences in teaching learners with mild ADHD to make a meaningful contribution to the study. The sample size was 25 participants, which included 18 Class Teachers, 3 School Administrators and 4 MoE Officials. The study used homogeneous purposive sampling techniques to select class teachers and school administrators and expert purposive sampling techniques to select all MoE officials responsible for special education in the district. This was based on the premises that participants had experiences in the teaching of learners with mild ADHD.

To collect data for this study, the main instruments that were used included in-depth interviews guide, Focus Group Discussions guide and observation checklist. This provided a triangulation of instruments for the data that was collected. Thematic analysis was used to analyze data. Thematic analysis is a method for identifying, analyzing, organizing,

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describing and reporting themes found within a data set (Clarke and Braun 2006). Qualitative data from interviews and observations were cleaned, transcribed and coded into themes and sub-themes that emerged during data collection. This was done by carefully listening to the recorded conversations in order to interpret, reduce and code key responses into major and sub-themes in relation to the research purpose. The other considerations during thematic analysis are those that relate to consistency and specificity in responses (Creswell, 2014). This was achieved through probes as data was being collected and analyzed simultaneously.

FINDINGS

The findings on the perceived teachers' conception on teaching of learners with mild ADHD was based on the three set objectives. These were teachers' understanding of teaching learners with mild ADHD, teachers' perceptions of teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive schools and the support provided by teachers teaching learners with mild ADHD.

How Teachers' understanding influence the way they teach learners with mild ADHD

On the first objective of the study, which focused on teachers' understanding of teaching learners with mild ADHD, it was found that teachers had mixed views on teaching learners with ADHD in inclusive schools. Minority participants (Seven out of 18) expressed adequate understanding of teaching learners with ADHD while the majority of the participants (11 out of 18) cited limited understanding of teaching of learners with ADHD in inclusive primary schools. Participants were asked to describe their understanding on teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools. Minority teachers cited reasons why they felt they had adequate understanding of teaching learners with ADHD. They stated that they had adequate understanding because they were trained to teach learners with ADHD, were self-motivated to teach learners with ADHD and able to control the behaviors of learners in the classes.

Inadequate training in Special Education

The study found that some teachers had limited understanding on the teaching learners with mild ADHD because they had inadequate training in Special Education. Most of the teachers revealed that during teaching they were unable to attend to learners with mild ADHD because they had little knowledge in terms of how to teach such learners. Majority of the teachers had certificates in Special Education and very few had diplomas and degrees in Special Education. Most teachers reported that they only had a component of Special Education during their training at college, which was not specifically for learners with mild ADHD. The above views were reflected in the response from one of the female teacher

participant from school 2 during Focus Group Discussion <FGD 2 T8F> who stated that:

"I only have a certificate for my teaching qualification, some of the issues regarding special education I may not know them" (31.05.23).

During Focus Group Discussion, a female participant from school 1 during Focus Group Discussion <SCH 1 T4F> mentioned that:

"Some of the teaching methods, strategies and techniques used by teachers' in classrooms for learners with ADHD are not appropriate for such learners" (29.05.23).

The lack of appropriate training and skills in teaching learners with ADHD affected the way teachers perceived the learners with ADHD in many ways. From the findings, without knowledge and skills, teachers may think the ADHD learners with inadvertently misdemeanors and fail to provide deliberate support for them. Lack of qualifications affects the self-confidence in providing services to the learners. The following excerpts demonstrate that teachers failed to pay attention to the needs of learners. A MoE official confirms this when he said:

"Most teachers have not paid attention to learners with mild ADHD in the classroom. For instance, some teachers use teaching methods such as class discussion and group discussion that are not meant for learners with mild ADHD" (MoE 2 09.06.23).

Contributing on the same, a male teacher participant from school 3 <FGD 3 T15M> acknowledged that:

"I did not receive such training at college and university so I don't know how to deal with such learners in school so I find very difficult to control their aggressive behavior that they sometimes portray" (02.06.23).

From the findings, it is clear that lack of training and skills in teaching and managing ADHD in primary school created negative perceptions of the learners. The lack of knowledge and skills is due to inadequate training in special education. Thus, it is difficult for teachers with inadequate knowledge of ADHD to create a positive position or image of their learners, labelling them as though they were permanently ADHD. This affects learner performance and their inclusion in school. For instance, from one of voices in FGDs, one participant said

"Madam, learners with ADHD struggle to make friends. Good relationships require someone to be aware of others thoughts and feelings however, these learners don't

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mind or understand others” (<FGD 2T8F> 29.05.23).

Another says

“Learners with ADHD have a decreased ability to self-regulate their actions towards others. This causes relationships to be overly tense and fragile. For instance, in the classroom they force themselves to do what they want on their friends without considering the feelings and thoughts of their friends” (<FGD 1T2F> 31.05.23).

These seem to be perceptions created of ADHD learners owing to not knowing how to interact with them, to lack of training and knowledge about the condition. Once with positively perceived, they can possibly reciprocate positively.

Teachers' perceptions of teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools

Concerning the second objective, the study unveiled different perceptions that teachers had towards teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive school. The findings revealed two significant types of perceptions, which included positive and negative perceptions of teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools.

Concerning teachers' attitudes towards learners with mild ADHD, participants were asked to describe the perceptions of teachers towards learners with mild ADHD in inclusive schools. Teacher participants confirmed that some teachers had negative attitude towards such learners. For instance, they preferred them to go to the Special Unit or Special Education school. Turning away from such learners from school thinking they were a problem in school was not a solution to a problem. Contributing on the same findings, one female teacher participant from school 1 during Focus Group Discussion <FGD T5 F> had this to say:

“They are very few teachers that are interested in teaching them because they feel they need to move with these children who are so called normal which is very dangerous as we really need to include them in the mainstream. Some teachers have a negative attitude toward these learners with such a condition” (31.05.23).

In line with the findings above, a male teacher participant from school 2 during Focus Group Discussion <SCH3 ADM 3F> said:

“Madam, teachers think that there is much to do with such learners hence resort to shunning away such learners” (02.06.23).

Negative perceptions can lead to dropping out of school because learners with ADHD can feel neglected. This was

revealed by participants and educators should note for action. One selected verbatim says as follows:

“Madam, the learners with ADHD drop out of school because of their condition which requires a lot of attention by the teacher or the caregiver. They need concerted efforts in order for them to succeed in their education. Learning should not end only at school but it should continue up to their homes, additional support is also needed to help these learners in the classroom as well as their homes” (<FGD 3T13> 02.06.23).

It was evident from the findings of the study that teachers had a negative attitude towards learners with ADHD. For example, teachers confirmed that they preferred learners with mild ADHD to go to the Special Unit or Special Education school, teachers avoided these learners and thought they were a problem in school because they were not able to sit in one place for a long period instead they were found everywhere in class without concentration.

How teachers' perceptions influenced support for learners with ADHD negatively

Other teachers had negative perceptions which affected the nature of support provided to learners with ADHD. The following findings indicate negatively in the way learners with ADHD are supported.

Huge class sizes

Findings indicate that there was over enrolment in classes, whose huge numbers affected the nature class tasks given to the learners with ADHD. One of the MoE officials had this to say:

“It's the issue of class population. Most schools are over enrolled and these learners are not identified so they are given the same work with other learners because teachers may not know that these learners have challenges” (<MoE 2M> 09.06.2023).

Even learners observed the issue of over enrolment as a challenge.

“Madam you would find that it is very hard to handle such learners because of the Class enrolment. These learners always lag behind they do not finish work give to them

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with other learners in class" (<FGD 3 T13 F> 02.06.23).

Now, when all learners are given the same work, it makes learning difficult for the category of learners under this study because they may require some differentiated work for us to see meaningful learning in them. Over enrolment certainly affected the manner of support for the learners.

Lack of specialization

While lack of specialization affected teachers understanding, it also influenced the support to the learners.

"At upper section it's difficult to attend or give attention to them because there is specialization. Teachers with learners only for 40 minutes and when it elapse they need to move on to another class" (<SCH 2 AD2 M>31.05.2023).

Sneaking out of class

"They usually sneak out of the classroom without the knowledge of the teacher. Teachers have to start looking for them in school. Following the time table when teaching these learners becomes difficult because they may not be found in classroom the time you were supposed to teach them" (<FGD3 T14 F>02.06.23).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study on the first objective on teachers' understanding of teaching learners with ADHD revealed that teachers had mixed views on their understanding of teaching learners with ADHD in schools. Few teachers reported that they had adequate understanding of teaching learners with ADHD in inclusive primary schools. These findings were in line with Dwarika et al. (2021) who found that teachers understanding of teaching learners with ADHD appeared limited as they faced challenges of dealing with such learners in the classroom. This was also supported by Jaye (2020), who revealed that teachers had limited knowledge regarding the symptoms of ADHD. Most of the participants revealed that during teaching they were unable to attend to learners with ADHD because they had little knowledge of teaching these learners. In terms of qualification, it was reported that some teachers had primary school teaching certificates while others had diplomas and a few had first degrees. Some teachers confessed that their initial teacher training did not equip them to teach learners with ADHD. These findings were not quite different from Sikabule (2019) who found that most of the teachers had little understanding about the existence of ADHD and were unable to identify learners with this condition.

On the finding that teachers had negative perceptions towards the learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools, there is a departure current policy practices that states that teachers should have knowledge and skills so that they were able to provide quality education and inclusive education for learners in the schools. Negative Perceptions of teaching learners with mild ADHD in primary schools has implications on the quality education and inclusive education provided to learners in the schools. For example, the teachers' negative perceptions on teaching learners with mild ADHD made them give labels and have negative attitudes towards learners, describing learners as distractive, over reacted, difficult to control. This has serious implication on the provision of quality education and inclusive education for learners in the schools. The findings of this study were not quite different from those of Naidoo (2019) who noted that teachers had different perceptions when teaching learners with mild ADHD, which often stemmed from lack of knowledge or understanding of mild ADHD in schools. However, the findings of this study differs from the findings of Lawrence et al. (2017) on Teachers' experiences and perceptions of students with mild ADHD, which revealed that culture and gender influenced teacher perceptions and mild ADHD classroom strategies were based on anecdotal experience. Teachers experienced guilty and worry while negotiating the learner's needs, school system constraints and family issues.

Framework to support teachers and learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools

The emergent framework is nicknamed *Kabwe's Framework (KF)* to support teachers and learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools. Kabwe's Framework (KF) addresses the implications that emanated from the teachers' limited understanding, and negative perceptions, which affect the overall quality education and inclusive education for learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools.

The positive teachers' understanding, and perceptions need to be upheld because these variables and ethos lead to quality education and inclusion of learners with ADHD in inclusive primary schools. The negative teachers' understanding, perceptions and support strategies need to be identified and addressed so that the ultimate goal of quality education and inclusion is realized.

According to Kabwe's Framework, teachers' limited understanding leads to lack of quality inclusive education characterised by inability to handle learners, inappropriate use of teaching methods, strategies and techniques and the inability to control learners. Thus, teachers' limited understanding had implications on the nature of services received by learners in schools and should be addressed to promote health inclusion.

According to the findings that informed the framework the negative perceptions portrayed by teachers included negative attitude, describing learners as distractive, inattentive

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learners, over reactant learners, uncontrollable and unreliable. These negative perceptions affected the teaching and learning of learners with mild ADHD in schools.

In the context of this study, the KF states that minimum support is based on the already built perceptions. Therefore, limited teachers' understanding, negative perception and limited support leads to no quality education, no inclusive education, poor academic performance and poor services offered to learners with ADHD. This framework therefore, encourages teachers to implement the four strategies to ease the learning of learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools. If these support strategies are implemented, learners with mild ADHD would benefit in inclusive primary schools.

On the other hand, if these strategies were not implemented, the overall quality education and inclusive education for learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools would be compromised.

The implication therefore is that limited teachers' understanding, negative perception and limited support leads to no quality education, no inclusive education, poor academic performance and poor services offered to learners with ADHD. It is for this reason that there is a need to design a framework that is intended to support teachers and learners with mild ADHD in inclusive schools in order to promote inclusive education. The following figure illustrates the framework:

Source: Researcher's Proposed Framework of Support Strategies (2024)

The framework above shows a linkage among three key variables, which include teachers understanding, and perceptions for learners with mild ADHD and further what it means for quality education and inclusive education for learners with ADHD in inclusive primary schools.

The positive teachers' understanding, perceptions and support strategies need to be upheld because these variables and ethos lead to quality education and inclusion of learners with ADHD in inclusive primary schools. The negative teachers' understanding, and perceptions need to be identified and addressed so that the ultimate goal of quality education and inclusion is realized. If limited teachers' understanding, negative perception and limited support are not identified and addressed, there would be no quality inclusive education, poor academic performance and poor services offered to

learners with ADHD, and the ultimate goal of quality education and inclusion would not be realized.

Teachers' understanding influences the perception of teachers towards learners with mild ADHD. Similarly, teachers' perception influences the nature of support provided to learners with ADHD. Minimum support is based on the already built perception.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is evident that the study revealed mixed views on teachers understanding of teaching learners with ADHD in inclusive primary schools. Few teachers had adequate understanding and most of the teachers had limited understanding due to inadequate preparation in Special education. Therefore, negative perception and limited support leads to no quality

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education, no inclusive education, poor academic performance and poor services offered to learners with ADHD. Hence should be addressed. To address the negative perceptions on teaching of learners with ADHD in inclusive primary schools, there was need to design a framework that is intended to support teachers and learners with mild ADHD in inclusive schools in order to promote inclusive education. The framework was named Kabwe's Framework (KF) of supporting teachers and learners with mild ADHD in inclusive schools. Based on the findings and conclusion, the following are the recommendations made: Schools in Lusaka should:

1. Provide capacity building for teachers of learners with mild ADHD. This would help in addressing the challenges of teacher incompetence in teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools
2. Facilitate workshops and seminars to sensitize teachers on how to handle learners with mild ADHD. This would also address the teachers' negative perceptions of teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools.
3. Collaborate with the Ministry of Health in raising awareness about the increasing numbers of mild ADHD in schools. This would enhance positive perceptions of teaching learners with mild ADHD in inclusive primary schools
4. Facilitate local participation in CPDs where they would educate school administrators, parents and relevant stakeholders on the value of understanding ADHD learners.

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